

A STUDY ON WORK STRESS MANAGEMENT

SHAIK KARISHMA

MBA Student, Saveetha School of Management, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences (SIMATS), Saveetha University, Chennai. Email: karishshaik23@gmail.com

Dr. GIGI G.S

Assistant Professor, Saveetha School of Management, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences (SIMATS), Saveetha University, Chennai. Email: gigigs.ssm@saveetha.com

Abstract

The issue of work related can be determined as a drawback factor for the employees where the effective measures and interest shall be taken into consideration by the company executives or managers to overcome such issues. As the increasing growth of new innovation, technology development as well as the idea to stand different from other competitive companies has come to rule the business world, therefore with the increasing development comes the greater responsibility. Thus, the sole purpose of this article is to put adequate importance on work stress management. The study determines the in depth analysis of the matter that generates the work stress issues. The present paper is obliged to highlight various perceptions of the employees from different sectors.

Keywords: Work related stressors, physical symptoms, employee wellbeing, and change in behaviour.

INTRODUCTION

The term work stress management is one of the major focused topics in the organization behaviour study which can be determined as a systematic study and application of knowledge about how the individuals and group acts within an organization where they work. Here the stress management can also be identified or denoted as one of the influencing factors regarding how the stress affects the individuals behaviour within the organization. Stress management can be a very useful or may be a helpful factor to overcome or reduce the negative impact of stress faced by the employees which can cause a distress in their health as well as their well-being. Stress management can be considered as a tool, strategies and techniques to reduce the overload of stress by measuring and learning ways of behavioural as well as intellectual that can reduce it.

The stress cannot be completely ignored and can occur at any time, hence the human resource departments need to have optimum strategies and policies to overcome the stressful situation and assist the employees in an effective and efficient way for the employees to lead a happy life in the work environment and keep the company running successfully. "Stress is one of the anxieties of any employee in the modern workplace" (Cam T.H. Tran, Hieu T.M. Tran, Huy T.N. Nguyen, Dung N. Mach, Hung S.P. Phan, Bahaudin G. Mujtaba, D.B.A., 2020).

The change in the action of an individual and ordinary response of the body changes when stress tends to arise. The mental, physical and emotional reaction will be used by any individual to express the change. The organization environment, body and thoughts are the influencing factors to determine the stress of an individual (Cleveland Clinic, 2015). The companies must realize and consider the significance of stress management and employee or initiate innovative

ideas regarding stress management to reduce the stress level of the employees and help them perform their work in a relaxed manner to ensure a productive work (Dr. Rohit Bansal 2018).

Working environment stress is a quiet, and frequently ignored, factor which disables representative wellbeing and efficiency. It influences the laborers as well as contributes altogether to a decrease in an organization's general achievement. Managers should start to handle this troubling worry to make a better, more secure, and more useful work environment (corporate wellness magazine).

After some time, constant work pressure can prompt a mental disorder known as burnout. Cautioning indications of burnout are overpowering weariness, criticism, and a feeling of inefficacy. Certain business related stressors are firmly connected with burnout. Models are having a lot of work or too little freedom, insufficient compensation, absence of local area between associates, injustice or affront, and a confound among work environment and individual qualities. (Nicole J 2019)

The analysis of in depth matters of resolving work environment stressors. Sound and glad representatives are more useful, so the managers of any organization should have a motivating force to handle work environment stress sooner rather than later. Contingent upon our work circumstance and different elements, we can be impacted by various sorts of business related pressure. The personal outlook and perceptions towards the external environment impacts on how an individual adapts themselves to the current or future circumstances. That is the reason, contingent upon our conditions, where an individual might get worried over certain things or others. Allow us to check out the circumstances and end results of business related pressure just as different sorts of business related pressure and how to manage. Similar researches have been conducted by many authors (Benita, 2021; Monica, 2021; David, Ahmed, Ganeshkumar & Sankar, 2020; Kumar, 2020; Kumar & Shree, 2019; Monica & Supriya, 2019; Mahesh & Uma Rani, 2019; Mahesh, Gigi, & Uma Rani, 2019; Robert & Monisha, 2019; Kumar & Shree, 2018).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Luthans (2008) characterized workforce pressure as "a versatile reaction to an outside circumstance that outcomes in physical, mental, as well as social deviations for an authoritative member". Mojdeh (2008) expressed that constant work-related pressure factors influence physical and emotional wellness, hazard of cardiovascular illness, clinical expenses and work execution. Accordingly, lessening work pressure factors is vital to forestall the advancement of stress related illnesses and to advance specialists wellbeing. Nursing being a profoundly upsetting occupation, constant natural work related pressure factors among attendants are related with work fulfillment and outer muscle issues, yet not with hazard pointers for cardiovascular infection, such pressure factors are additionally connected with the psychological and physical soundness of medical caretakers is significant for the nature of nursing care.

Manoj (2013) explored the representative pressure and showed that the working environment of numerous associations has become a climate with high-stress rates. High responsibility, tight cutoff times, stretch or ridiculous targets, absence of work fulfillment, long working hours, the strain to perform, and relational contentions are a portion of the fundamental variables prompting pressure among representatives. Stress impacts efficiency, confidence and the inspiration of laborers, and the benefit of associations. In addition, it causes medical conditions like a sleeping disorder, sorrow, and heart illness. Senova & Antosova (2014) Stress influences the administration as well as every other person working in the association ;consequently, due consideration ought to be given for its end Cleveland Clinic (2015) did a study on stress management and how the individuals body reacts during stress. It has been determined from the study that it is completely and naturally normal to be stressed sometime but, various measures shall be taken up to minimize the level of stress. Prasad, Vaidya, Kumar (2016) their research showed that, Workers who object to fault and superfluous analysis, forsake the interruptions and propensities for the objection, effectively take an interest in friendly exercises, and lessen the utilization of caffeine and sugar can raise their protection from stress

Rohit Bansal (2018) worked on stress management, this paper is discussed regarding the causes of stress and stress management techniques. This is a research journal based on how the management stress has become a major concern for the modern organization and how it is determined as a negative phenomena. D Holman, S Johnson (2018) in this study the authors have given an outline of pressure the board mediations (SMI) and audit the proof for their impacts on worker stress and prosperity. The study started by setting out a typology of SMI that classes SMI as indicated by level (i.e., the individual-level or association level) and concentration (i.e., a 'essential' center around changing the reasons for pressure or a 'optional' or 'tertiary' center around lessening pressure itself). B Espejo (2020), states that stress is recognized by continuous migraines, inordinate concern, consistent sluggishness, culpability, and anxiety. It additionally builds melancholy, disappointment, peevishness, outrage, a sleeping disorder, dissatisfaction, and bad dreams. Stress can likewise make individuals absent minded while experiencing issues focusing and simply deciding.

D Zapf, M Kern, F Tschan, D Holman (2021) taking on a work brain science point of view and drawing on work pressure and work plan writings, we diagram an extended model of feeling work, seeing feeling work necessities as occupation attributes and as a feature of more extensive undertaking prerequisites. Research on culture recommends that current outcomes are generally substantial for Western societies. M Magdincev aSopova, A Stojanovska-Stefanova (2021) this paper means to call attention to the job of the board in overseeing working environment stress, through convenient acknowledgment and discovery of the reasons for pressure and diminishing the effect of weight on workers. The outcomes of the examination affirm the theory that the effect of the COVID-19 infection is a vital variable in expanding stress in representatives at work. The aftereffects of the examination are the reason for making proposals for the administration in the execution of suitable exercises and a pressure on the board procedure. Napapilai Latthasaksiri (2021) A little pressure might be useful forever and work efficiency, however assuming that it lingers excessively enormous, it will absolutely hurt the association and its usefulness.

StutiJalan, Naval Grag (2021) the present study states the optimistic impact of workplace spirituality (WPS) to identify its connection with one of the most important issues for organizations, occupational stress (OS). The findings demonstrate the importance of accepting WPS as an effective tool for implementing. E Kevin Kelloway and Cary L. Cooper (2021) both strategic and considerable difficulties face analysts zeroed in on work and E. Kevin prosperity. The authors accepted what the specialists have contributed sections have done an exceptional occupation of summing up a voluminous writing and distinguishing research plans that would push the field ahead. Farinaz Havaei, Maura Macphee (2021) “Physical and emotional violence elicited psychological stress responses resulting in increased medication use”.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study used a quantitative survey method of data collection from a pool of respondents by asking multiple survey questions. A questionnaire was prepared for employees to find out their perception regarding work related stress. To prepare the questionnaire, work related stress, physical health issues and change in behaviour were considered as the factors influencing stress. The data collection through questionnaire was based on random sampling method. The questions were framed on a scalar basis (Likert’s 5 points scale). Data collection was based only on primary data. The data was collected through online survey and was analyzed using SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) statistical software and graphical representations were constructed using the statistical tool. From the analyzed data, suggestions and conclusions were drawn to improve the objective of the research paper on stress.

The article has been done in the metropolitan city Chennai. The city was chosen to study the work stress level of the employees. In this study a quantitative approach is adopted as well as the statistical methods used to determine the quality data for a coherent output in the form of facts and data. The software used to analyze and to gather data to assess the quality insights and findings is referred as SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science).

The main objective of the study is to analyze work stress management in various different sectors and provide suitable measures to overcome stress and to get clear insights regarding the withdrawal of stress overload within the organization. To analyze the collected data and to give adverse conclusion for the work related stress based on the study. The sample size was restricted to only 60. If it were increased, many more varied answers and suggestions would have been expected. The given short period of notice is one of the major drawbacks or the limitations faced during the article preparation. The fear of expressing the true facts among the respondents could be a limitation.

DATA ANALYSIS:

Table 1: Demographic Sketch of the Respondents

Demographic profile	Frequency	Percentage	
Gender	Male	29	48.3
	Female	31	51.7
Age	20 – 30 years	40	66.7
	31 -40 years	12	20
	41 – 50 years	5	8.3
	More than 50 years	3	5
No. of members in the family	3 – 4	39	65
	5 – 6	18	30
	7 – 8	2	3.3
	More than 9	1	1.7
Level of education	UG	29	48.3
	PG	29	48.3
	PhD	2	3.3
Occupation	Educational / Academic	9	15
	Technical	24	40
	Service	14	23.3
	Health and medical	5	8.3
	Other	8	13.3
Years of experience	1 – 2 years	26	43.3
	3 – 4 years	15	25
	5 – 6 years	12	20
	More than 6 years	7	11
Marital Status	Single	42	70
	Married	18	30

This table shows that the majority of the respondents were Female (51.7) comparative to that of Male, which indicates that the females feel themselves more related towards the work stress in an organization. According to the data 66.7% of the respondents fall under the Age of 20 – 30, 31 – 40 years (20%) followed by 41 – 50 years (8.3%) and more than 50 years (5%). The level of education of the respondents are Undergraduate 48.3%, Postgraduate 48.3% and PhD 3.3%. The designation status of the respondents are Educational / Academic 15%, Technical 40%, Service 23.3% followed by Health and Medical 8.3% remaining other occupations over 13.3%. The level of experience of the respondents are 1 – 2 years (43.3%), 3 – 4 years (25%), 5 – 6 years (20%) followed by more than 6 years of experience at 11%. The majority of the respondent’s marital status is single (70%). Thus, it is clearly evident that the study on the Work Stress Management has generated responses from a varied range of respondents adequately representing the diversity data collected which generates in depth analysis of the study.

Table 2: Perception of the Respondents on Work Stress Management

S. no	Perception of the respondents regarding to the work stress management	Mean	Rank
1.	Company (or) organizational culture is one of the prevailing causes of stress.	2.92	8
2.	Bad management practices may increase stress.	1.87	2
3.	Role conflict can cause stress discomfort at work and lower employee motivation.	1.77	1
4.	Work related stress include conflict with co-workers (or) bosses, constant change and threat to job security.	1.77	1
5.	The poorer the physical work environment, the greater the level of stress, anxiety or trauma.	2.13	5
6.	Workers who are stressed at work are more likely to engage in unhealthy behaviour (ie, alcohol consumption, smoking cigarette, poor dietary pattern).	2.10	4
7.	Job stress can be a cause of adjustment insomnia.	2.10	4
8.	Work stress leads to irritability or outburst of anger.	2.10	4
9.	Low productivity accompanied by feelings of low achievement.	2.10	4
10.	It is important for employers to recognize work related stress as a significant health issue.	2.00	3
11.	High levels of work stress diminish creativity and initiative.	2.00	3
12.	Employees who face work stress tend to take more sick days leave or absenteeism.	2.13	5
13.	Providing on-site and distance counseling is considered helpful for the employees.	2.13	5
14.	Employees who spend a lot of time together, and the more comfortable they are, the less stress they will feel.	2.25	6
15.	Exercise and healthy living are two of your best weapons against workplace stress.	2.33	7

The mean score and rank are displayed in table 2. It shows variable “Results” including the highest mean score of 2.29 stress due to organization culture followed by exercise and healthy living as a weapon against stress 2.33. Followed by employees time spent together 2.25. Poor physical environment, absenteeism and availability of helpful counseling at 2.13. Whereas bad health patterns, insomnia, irritability, low feeling of achievement is ranked at 4 (2.10). Significant health issues, diminishing creativity and initiatives at 2.00. Bad management practice at 1.87. Discomfort at work and conflict with the co-workers 1.77. Therefore the mean inference can be concluded stating that respondents highly relate themselves towards the issues due to work stress in an organization.

Table 3: Anova

S.NO.	WORK STRESS MANAGEMENT	
	F	SIG
Age	1.271	.254
Marital status	1.731	.068
Family size	.460	.975
Educational level	1.472	.146
Occupation	1.316	.225
Level of experience	.865	.639

The significant value of Age, Marital Status, Family Size, Educational Level, Occupation, Level of Experience is greater than 0.05 accepting the null hypothesis. The table shows that there is no significant difference among Age, Marital Status, Family Size, Educational Level, Occupation, and Level of Experience with respect to the work stress management.

CONCLUSION:

The research solely focuses on the work stress management which plays a vital role regarding the performance input of the employees and therefore how it affects the organizational output as well as the individual, organizational goals and aspects. According to the survey's findings, the majority of the respondents felt that work-related stress is one of the foremost issues that can be incurred from various ways (external as well as internal forces). Hence such issues can be resolved through the means of a positive workforce environment, performance appreciation, on-site or distant counseling, maximum time spent with the employees where they can understand each and every person's views and ideas which shall be highly appreciated. Thus creating an interpersonal relationship can help the employees overcome the stress issues where the quote, in every formal organization there is an informal organization is an apt suggestion for stress relief in an organization.

REFERENCES

- Bansal, R. (2018). Stress management at workplace. *Internacional Journal of Techno-Management Research*, 5(04), 29-32.
- Benita, M. S. (2021). Are the student migrants satisfied with life? Effect of acculturative stress and perceived discrimination. *International Journal of Education Economics and Development*, 12(1), 79-96.
- David, A., Ahmed, R. R., Ganeshkumar, C., & Sankar, J. G. (2020). Consumer Purchasing Process of Organic Food Product: An Empirical Analysis. *Calitatea*, 21(177), 128-132.
- Espejo, B. (2020). *Workplace Stress: A Supervisory Approach* (Doctoral dissertation, CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, NORTHRIDGE).
- Havaei, F., & MacPhee, M. (2021). Effect of workplace violence and psychological stress responses on medical-surgical nurses' medication intake. *Canadian journal of nursing research*, 53(2), 134-144.
- Holman, D., Johnson, S., & O'Connor, E. (2018). Stress management interventions: Improving subjective psychological well-being in the workplace. In *Handbook of well-being*. DEF Publishers.
- Jalan, S., & Garg, N. (2022). Exploring linkages between workplace spirituality and occupational stress among Indian police personnel. *South Asian Journal of Human Resources Management*, 9(1), 53-78.
- Kelloway, E. K., & Cooper, C. L. (2021). Introduction to A research agenda for workplace stress and wellbeing. *A Research Agenda for Workplace Stress and Wellbeing*, 3-14.
- Kumar, P. P. (2020). Effectiveness of Marketing Strategy Formulation in Biomedical Healthcare Industry.
- Kumar, P. P., & Shree, K. C. (2018). Determinants of Vendor-Client Relationship in Medical Equipment Industry. *Indian Journal of Public Health Research & Development*, 9(10).
- Kumar, P. P., & Shree, K. C. (2019). Green human resource management: A access device to evade exhaustion of natural resources. *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, 8(11), 740-743.

- Latthasaksiri, N. (2021). Stress Management at Workplace in Challenging Situations. RICE Journal of Creative Entrepreneurship and Management, 2(3), 31-38.
- Luthans (2008) Published in The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science 44:1 (March 2008), pp. 48–70
- MagdincevaSopova, M., Stojanovska-Stefanova, A., & Aleksoski, O. (2021). Employee stress management caused by the impact of the covid-19 virus: the Macedonian case. SocioBrains, (80), 15-27.
- Manoj, A. S. (2013). An analytical study on employee stress with special reference to information technology companies in Technopark: A Kerala experience. International Journal of Advanced Research in Management and Social Sciences, 2(11), 156-157.
- Monica, B. (2021). The Effect of IT Employees' Engagement on Work Attitudes Through Cloud Computing Services. In Recent Advances in Technology Acceptance Models and Theories (pp. 497-507). Springer, Cham.
- Monica, B. S., & Supriya, M. V. (2019). Acculturative stress of internal migrants: impact on work attitudes. International Journal of Human Resources Development and Management, 19(2), 150-165.
- Prasad, K. D. V., Vaidya, R., & Kumar, V. A. (2016). Teacher's performance as a function of occupational stress and coping with reference to CBSE affiliated school teachers in and around Hyderabad: a multinomial regression approach. Psychology, 7(13), 1700-1718.
- S Mojdeh (2008) Relationship between nurse's stress and environmental - occupational factors IJNMR 2008; 13(1): 1-5
- Seňová, A., & Antořová, M. (2014). Work stress as a worldwide problem in present time. Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences, 109, 312-316.
- V. J, Mahesh & Uma Rani, P.(2019). Impact of Promotional Strategies on Viewers of Kollywood Movies. International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering, 8(10), pp. 1140–1144
- V. J, Mahesh, Gigi, G.S., & Uma Rani, P. (2019). Movie promotional strategies in tamil film industry-the contemporary access. International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering, 8(11), pp. 712–717
- William Robert P, R. Monisha (2019) .A Research on Factors of Forex Procedures in Private Bank. International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering, 8(11s), 777- 781.Scopus Indexed-e-ISSN:2278-3075.
- Zapf, D., Kern, M., Tschan, F., Holman, D., & Semmer, N. K. (2021). Emotion work: A work psychology perspective. Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior, 8, 139-172.